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EFFECTS OF LONG TERM HYGROTHERMAL CYCLING ON GLASS/VINYL ESTER COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: In this study, glass/vinyl ester composite was exposed to hygrothermal cycling between -18°C /dry/4 hours and 80°C /saturated steam/17 hours. The total exposure duration was up to 10,000 hours, with correspondingly 350 freeze/thaw cycles. Weight changes of the composite were recorded at the end of each freeze and thaw duration. Mechanical and thermal property variations as functions of exposure time were also characterized. It was found that weight gains of the composite, undergone a significant increment during initial 1,000 hours, gradually dropped to zero after extended long term cycling of about 10,000 hours. The compression strength was initially increased about 10% during the early stage of the cycling and then gradually decreased with a continuous increasing in cycling exposure duration. Glass transition temperature showed a rapid increase in initial cycling stage, then followed by a moderate rate of increment. Thermal decomposition temperature as a function of the hygrothermal exposure duration had a similar trend, but showed a near leveling-off with further extended hygrothermal cyclic exposures.

KEYWORDS: Vinyl ester composite, hygrothermal aging, environmental durability.

INTRODUCTION

Glass/vinyl ester composites are commonly used structural materials. However, the large number of hydroxyl groups in vinyl ester molecules makes the composites prone to absorb moisture. Large moisture absorption, if combined with elevated temperature, may lead to deterioration of service performance and long-term durability of the composites [1-2]. Therefore, it is important to study the moisture absorption behaviors, as well as environmental effects on the properties of the composites.

The research work in this project has been divided into three parts as shown in Fig.1. The first part was studying the effects of accelerated thermal and hygrothermal exposures on the microstructures and mechanical properties of the composite [3], and the second was of investigating hygrothermal cycling effects on the thermal and mechanical properties and characterizing moisture absorption behaviors of the composite during the cycling. The latter was presented on ICCM12 [4]. This study, as a third part, is a continuation of those previous research work.

In present work, the glass/vinyl ester composite samples were further exposed to long term freeze/thaw cycling up to 10,000 hours. The objectives of this research work were to extend the characterizations of thermal and mechanical property changes of the composite during long term hygrothermal cycling, to develop an understanding of hygrothermal effects on the composite, and to provide reference data and some guidelines for components design and environmental durability evaluations of the composites.

Fig.1 Research work in studying environmental durability of glass/vinyl ester composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material used in this study was S2-glass fabric/vinyl ester 411-350 composite fabricated by vacuum aided resin infusion and cured at room temperature. The composite panels were cut into specimens with dimensions of 15x15x10 mm before the environmental exposures.

The glass/vinyl ester composite specimens were alternatively held in a container saturated with steam at elevated temperature and a freezer to simulate freeze/thaw cycling process. The hygrothermal cycling conditions were at 80°C/saturated steam (98% relative humidity) for 17 hours and then at -18°C/dry for 4 hours. The total hygrothermal cycling duration was about 10,000 hours with more than 350 cycles.

Weight changes were recorded at the end of each freeze and thaw duration. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermogravimetry analysis (TGA), and mechanical compression testing were performed to investigate the changes of thermal mechanical property, thermal decomposition behavior, and mechanical property of the composite during the cycling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Moisture Absorption during Hygrothermal Cycling

Weight gain of the composite specimen as a function of the hygrothermal exposure duration is shown in Fig.2. It can be seen that weight gain of the composite increased significantly during early stage of hygrothermal cycling (up to about 1,000 hours) and then started a reverse trend. One of the most important features of the absorption behaviors upon the extended long term hygrothermal cycling was that weight gain of the composite gradually dropped to zero after about 10,000 hours. This was believed to be caused by decomposition of the resin after long

time environmental exposures. The phenomenon of steady decreasing in weight gain with extended exposure time can be referred to as one kind of non-Fickian fluid behavior and was also reported by other researchers [4].

It also can be noticed that, as reported in our earlier work [5], the glass/vinyl ester composite showed a rapid moisture absorption at the beginning of each freeze period and a noticeable desorption at the beginning of each thaw period. Possible reasons for such cyclic moisture absorption and desorption during each freezing and thawing cyclic period might be due to the difference in thermal expansion coefficients between resin and fibers, as well as cyclic thermal expansion and contraction of resin during the cycling. Some micro-defects on the surface of the composite specimens, such as microcracks and cavities, would tend to be “open” when the composite surface experiences a sudden temperature drop, thus leading to a higher absorption rate at the beginning of freeze period. On the other hand, when the composite undergoes a sudden temperature rise, these defects with open space tend to be “close” due to thermal expansion, therefore, “squeezing” water out of the composite surface.

Fig.2 Moisture absorption/desorption curve of glass/vinyl ester composite during long term hygrothermal cyclic exposure.

2. Effects of Hygrothermal Cycling on Mechanical Properties

Variation of compression strength as a function of hygrothermal cycling number, *i.e.*, exposure duration, is shown in Fig.3. It can be seen that the compression strength was increased by about 13% during the early stage (up to 50 cycles) of the cycling. This is believed to be a result of postcure of vinyl ester at the elevated temperature which led to an increase in crosslinking degree of the matrix. Beyond that, compression strength of the composite decreased gradually with a continuous increase in cycling process duration, indicating that increased physical and chemical degradations in resin became predominant which overcame the influence from the postcure. After experienced about 300 hygrothermal cycles (about 8,600 hours), the compression strength of the composite had a drop of about 12% from its

peak value obtained in the early stage of the cycling, thus brought it back to its original as-received level. It seems that the decreasing trend of compression strength with increasing exposure cycling would continue if the hygrothermal cycling process further extends.

These preliminary results indicate that although the exposure temperatures used in this study (80°C and -18°C) were almost the extremes of temperatures used in practical applications for this kind of material, the mechanical properties of the composite did not show a significant change. The results also suggest that glass/vinyl ester composites used in this study were not fully cured during their fabrication process. If they are used in an environment of elevated temperatures, their physical and mechanical properties could initially undergo some changes with time.

Fig.3 Compression strength as a function of hygrothermal cycling duration.

3. Effects of Hygrothermal Cycling on Thermal Mechanical Properties

Glass transition temperature, T_g , is a measurement of thermal mechanical properties of materials. Here, T_g of the composite was measured by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) to investigate hygrothermal cycling effects on thermal mechanical properties. Fig.3 shows T_g as a function of hygrothermal cycling.

Fig.3 Glass transition temperature, T_g , as a function of hygrothermal cycling.

It was found that during early stage T_g was increased with an increasing in cycling time at a rapid rate. After the first 100 exposure cycles, an increment of 20°C was reached. Beyond that, the increment of T_g became moderate. The initial higher rate of increases in T_g is also an indication of postcure effects on the resin during its exposure to elevated temperature. The results suggest that the composite might have modified thermal mechanical properties when exposed to certain level of elevated temperature.

4. Hygrothermal Cycling Effects on Thermal Stability

Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) was used to study the thermal stability of the composite upon hygrothermal cycling. From Fig.4., it can be seen that thermal decomposition temperature as a function of hygrothermal exposure time has a similar trend as that of glass transition temperature. It was increased by about 20°C during the first 150 cycles and thereafter almost leveled off. Since the change of thermal stability is a reflection of chemical structure change in materials, the initial increase of thermal decomposition temperature indicated that there were chemical structure changes of the composite during that stage.

Fig.4 Variation of thermal decomposition temperature with hygrothermal cycling duration.

CONCLUSIONS

Weight gains of the glass/vinyl ester composite, after a rapid increase in the early stage (up to 1,000 hours), gradually reduced to zero after about 350 cycles (10,000 hours) under the hygrothermal cyclic exposure. Compression strength increased about 13% during the first 50 cycles and then gradually dropped. After 300 cycles of hygrothermal exposure, it decreased about 14% from the peak value obtained in the earlier stage back to that of as-received. Glass transition temperature showed a rapid increment in the first 100 exposure cycles and then the change became moderate. Thermal decomposition temperature also increased in the early stage of the cycling and then almost leveled off with further extended hygrothermal cyclic exposure.

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